

OBJECTIVE AND SUBJECTIVE FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH'S AESTHETIC THINKING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15694945>

Abstract. This thesis-article analyzes the factors influencing the development and enhancement of aesthetic thinking among youth. In particular, it explores the interrelation between objective factors (such as the social environment, cultural heritage, the education system, and technological advancement) and subjective factors (such as personal interests, inner world, and creative potential). The paper also highlights the role of aesthetic education in society and its impact on the spiritual and moral development of young people. Based on the research findings, effective directions and recommendations are proposed for the advancement of aesthetic thinking among youth.

Keywords: aesthetic thinking, youth, objective factors, subjective factors, aesthetic education.

Аннотация. В данной тезисной статье анализируются факторы, влияющие на развитие и повышение эстетического мышления молодежи. В частности, раскрывается взаимосвязь между объективными (социальная среда, культурное наследие, система образования, технологический прогресс) и субъективными (личные интересы, внутренний мир, творческий потенциал) факторами. Также освещается роль эстетического воспитания в обществе и его влияние на духовно-нравственное становление молодежи. По результатам исследования предлагаются эффективные направления и рекомендации по развитию эстетического мышления у молодежи.

Ключевые слова: эстетическое мышление, молодежь, объективные фактор, субъективные факторы, эстетическое воспитание.

In modern society, aesthetic thinking is not just a concept related to art, but an important factor determining the socio-moral formation of a person, his aesthetic attitude to life. Aesthetics is not only the understanding and creation of beauty, but also the process of perceiving, appreciating and applying it in life.

According to world and national thinkers, through aesthetic education, a person discovers his inner beauty and creates a beautiful environment in society.¹

In the formation of aesthetic thinking of young people, the role of the social environment is, first of all, incomparable. Aesthetic norms are instilled in the mind through the family, educational institutions, and the media. G. Santayana emphasizes that aesthetic values are formed in the mind not by chance, but inextricably linked with cultural traditions and the needs of society.²

Cultural heritage is a rich source of transmitting the aesthetic thinking of a nation from generation to generation. Folk oral art, folk applied art, national architectural monuments instill a love of beauty in the younger generation. According to T.W.Adorno, art is a powerful social tool that awakens aesthetic consciousness and determines the level of cultural development of society.³

Also, one of the factors influencing aesthetic thinking is the education system. According to M.Greene, the school should be a place that provides not only information, but also aesthetic experience. In the process of education, a person matures through a sense of beauty and artistic thinking.⁴ From this perspective, it is important to develop innovative approaches, thinking through art, and critical thinking in aesthetic education classes today.

In addition, technological progress is creating new forms of aesthetic thinking. Digital art, artificial intelligence-based visual representations, and AR/VR environments show that aesthetic experience for young people is no longer limited to galleries and museums. P. Goldie and E. Schellekens emphasize that works of art created through digital technologies are shaping new aesthetic norms.⁵

Another important factor shaping the aesthetic thinking of young people is the inner world, interests and creative potential of the individual. Each person perceives beauty differently, which is associated with his individual life experience and psychological state. T. Almeida-Rocha and colleagues in their study found that aesthetic development among young people occurs precisely in the context of a combination of emotional and cognitive factors.⁶

Aesthetic education directly affects the moral views and spiritual maturity of young people. In the works of the Uzbek thinker A. Navoi, the ideas of beauty and perfection are also considered as a single philosophical and aesthetic concept. According to him, a true person manifests himself in society as a mature person through his striving for beauty and appreciation of it.⁷

In conclusion, the development of aesthetic thinking among young people requires a comprehensive approach based on a combination of objective (social

environment, cultural heritage, education and technology) and subjective (interest, thinking, creativity) factors. Improving the system of aesthetic education based on philosophical and aesthetic approaches, using innovative tools and expanding the cultural and communicative environment with young people is an important strategic direction.

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